

STOCK MARKET DEVELOPMENT AND FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT

Akinyemi A. Ajibola, Nnoli T. Ikenna, Hassan C. Onyohu, Njogo O.
Bibiana and Ogbeide Vera

Department of Economics, Accounting and Finance, Bells University of Technology, Ota

Corresponding Author's email: nnolis22@yahoo.com

Abstract

This study examines the impact of stock market development on foreign direct investment inflow to Nigeria. Secondary data from 1981 to 2019 was used for the study. Data was analyzed using Granger causality and Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root test, Johansen co-integration test and Error correction model regression. The results of Granger causality revealed that while uni-directional causality was found running from each of stock market capitalization ratio and Turnover ratio respectively to Foreign direct investment inflow, Bi-directional causality was found between total value of stocks traded ratio and Foreign direct investment inflow. Error correction model regression revealed that stock market capitalization ratio, Turnover ratio and total value of stocks traded ratio respectively have a negative and statistically insignificant impact on Foreign direct investment inflow in Nigeria amongst other findings. The study recommends based on its findings that urgent and appropriately sequenced stock market reforms be undertaken so as to reverse the adverse effects of stock market development indicators on FDI inflow. Further increased financial openness of the Nigeria economy should be promoted as part of financial liberalization reforms so as to attract quality firms to the Nigeria stock exchange.

Keywords: Stock market, foreign direct investment, Turnover ratio, Trade Openness

Introduction

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) is an investment made in host countries by foreign individuals or companies. It is made by non-nationals of a country in order to regulate the activities of firms in the host country in which the foreign direct investment is made. Through Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) foreign owners gain control over the behavior of firms in the host country in which the investment is made (Oseni & Enilolobo, 2011). Further foreign firms undertake FDI in seeking to benefit from cheaper costs of production in host countries (Aktar et al, 2013) Firms in advanced countries have moved much of their labor-intensive production to developing nations where wages are lower. For example significant FDI from developed countries has found its way to China on account of cheap cost of labor in China (Boermansb, Roelfsemaab, & Yi, 2009).

According to UNCTAD Global Value Chains (2013) Nigeria has attracted high foreign direct investment inflows and in 2012 attracted FDI inflows to the sum of US\$7.03bn surpassing inflows to other African countries of the share of Global FDI inflow to Africa. Thus Nigeria has performed creditably in attracting world foreign direct investment inflows which suggests optimism that

Nigeria is a highly rewarding economy in which to invest on account of the bright prospects of the Nigerian economy.

The stock market in Nigeria is the Nigeria stock exchange. The Nigeria stock exchange established in 1961 as a capital market in Nigeria provides an alternative source of capital to the banks for borrowing by investors both foreign and domestic, seeking to invest in the Nigeria economy. However, while the Nigeria banking system is at a relatively higher level of development relative to the Nigeria stock exchange, the Nigeria stock exchange remains important in contributing to the development of Nigeria's financial system (Omoruyi & Ahmed, 2014). Various factors have affected the development of the Nigeria stock exchange to date including weak quality institutions and poor regulation (Yartey & Adjasi, 2007), low liquidity, low foreign participation amongst other challenges. With respect to the role of liquidity of stock markets, Levine (2003) highlighted the role of increased liquidity for better development of the financial system amongst other factors. Liquidity defined as the ability to trade quickly will ensure that stocks can easily be traded as and when the need arises attracting yet further participation in the stock market and boosting the availability of credit.

Therefore, with the low level of development of the Nigeria stock exchange and the role played by various factors in its low level of development to date, this is likely to affect Nigeria through a number of channels of which foreign direct investment inflow is one. This may consequently have a ripple effect on the economy through affecting unemployment, poverty reduction amongst other socio-economic aspects of the Nigeria economy. In addition, stock market development by its nature has empirically been argued to feature two broad dimensions namely stock market size and liquidity. While stock market size is measured by the ratio of stock market capitalization to GDP, stock market liquidity is measured by turnover ratio and total value of shares traded ratio (Aigbovo&Izekor, 2015; Afeez&Kazeem, 2010; Amagwu, 2016). Thus a highly developed stock market will be one that features high values of all stock market development indicators and in the case of the Nigeria stock exchange exploring all three measures of stock market development for its impact on foreign direct investment inflow will shed light on how the Nigeria stock market can play a pivotal role in promoting increased foreign direct investment inflow to Nigeria. This is more so given the earlier mentioned invaluable benefits of foreign direct investment inflow to a developing economy as Nigeria. While stock market development may attract foreign direct investment to an economy such as that of Nigeria's, it is the case that foreign direct investment may promote stock market development given the potential that the stock market may develop in response to the inflow of foreign capital to a domestic economy through foreign direct investment.

Despite the hype of foreign investments especially that of foreign direct investments in Nigeria, the Nigeria stock market as a veritable tool to channel such foreign direct investment to Nigeria remains rather questionable and is yet to be fully appreciated (Olugbenga & Grace, 2015). This is aided by the fact that only few studies have explored the impact of stock market development for foreign direct investment especially in Nigeria (Umar, Ismail and Sulong, 2015). However the inability of the Nigeria stock market to channel foreign direct investments may be associated with challenges facing the Nigeria stock exchange especially as it concerns that of low liquidity and low market size amongst other challenges. The challenges while not specific to the Nigeria stock market but is general to stock markets in sub-Sahara Africa countries, may play a role in influencing foreigner perception of Nigeria as a hub for foreign direct investment with the potential of high returns in light of Nigeria's promising prospects. Consequently, foreign direct investment inflow to Nigeria will reduce and invaluable benefits will be lost by the Nigeria

economy. Hence, there is need to examine the impact of stock market development on foreign direct investment in Nigeria as the study aims to explore foreign direct investment traceable to the development of the Nigeria stock market. However, a methodological weakness of the only study to have examined stock market development is the potential multi-collinearity of all stock market development measures used in a singular model and giving rise to bias in results obtained. This is a second research gap of this study.

Thus a related research gap to be filled by the present study is the examination of the direction of causality between stock market development and foreign direct investment in flow activity in Nigeria. The present study is significant for a number of reasons. Firstly, on completion, it will serve as a reference and resource for researchers who might conduct studies similar to the present research. Secondly, the findings of this study will assist policy makers to understand the empirical association that exists between foreign direct investment and stock market development in Nigeria and thus policymakers will be able to formulate policies of benefit to the Nigeria economy. Thirdly, the findings of this study will also aid foreign investors in making sound decisions regarding taking advantage of opportunities for foreign direct investment in Nigeria in order to reap ample returns from profitable investments. Finally, the present study will contribute to the existing body of literature on foreign direct investment and stock market development in Nigeria and give rise to further research on the subject matter.

Literature Review

Studies examining foreign direct investment have been popularly studied in the context of developing countries. This may be explained by the fact that it is developing countries that are seeking for higher levels of growth given their present low growth and are most in need of foreign direct investment which tends to flow from developed countries. However also important for developing countries is a developed stock market to contribute to their economic growth efforts, and so together both foreign direct investment and stock market development may be argued to contribute positively to economic growth (Oseni & Enilolobo, 2011).

With regards to studies examining stock market development, KMMCB (2015) finds in Sri Lanka that volatile inflation rate and exchange rate together with higher deposit rate have curtailed stock market development in Sri Lanka.

Omodero and Ekwe (2017) examined the impact of foreign direct investment on stock market performance in Nigeria from 1985 to 2014 expressing foreign direct investment as a function of real GDP, consumer price index, real effective exchange rate, M2 Money supply, share price index, treasury bills and Nigeria stock exchange transactions. The study employed multivariate ordinary least squares regression. The findings revealed an insignificant impact of foreign direct investment on stock market performance in Nigeria. The study recommended policies that will attract foreign oil and gas firms as well as foreign telecommunication and agriculture firms to be listed on the Nigeria stock exchange.

The finding of insignificant impact of FDI on stock market in Nigeria by Omodero and Ekwe (2017) and Idenyi, Ifeyinwa and Obinna (2016) while consistent contrast with the findings in Ghana by Adam and Tweneboah (2008) who find over the period of 1991 to 2006 employing quarterly data and using impulse responses and Variance Decomposition from Vector Error Correction Model that increase in FDI significantly influence the development of stock market in Ghana, while a foreign direct investment has a significant long run relationship with stock market development. While the aforementioned studies have highlighted various factors affecting FDI, including stock market development and having contrasting findings, they nonetheless do not

examine the role of stock market development for foreign direct investment for which there are very few studies such as Bala-Umar, Ismail, and Sulong (2015).

Sulong (2015) who investigate the impact of the stock market variables on foreign direct investment using autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) in the presence of structural breaks (dummies) in Nigeria over the period of 1970 to 2013. The result suggests that the foreign direct investment (FDI) has a significant positive long-run impact on the value of the total stock transaction, but has a negative and significant effect on the rate of stock returns. However, the relationship between FDI and market capitalization ratio is not statistically significant. Based on these findings the stock market value of the total transaction promotes FDI and thus boosts economic growth and development in Nigeria.

Therefore in light of studies reviewed a substantial number of studies have explored the impact of foreign direct investment on stock market development, but very few examined the impact of stock market development on foreign direct investment. Further observed are contrasting findings regarding the impact of foreign direct investment on stock market development and the evident methodological weakness of all the studies examined whereby they fail to explore causality as a first step to establishing impact either of foreign direct investment on stock market development or stock market development on foreign direct investment. This represents the first research gap to be filled by this study. Further, with specific reference to the empirical studies which examined the impact of foreign direct investment on stock market development most studies do not find a significant impact of foreign direct investment. However the singular study which examined the impact of stock market development on foreign direct investment has a methodological concern in that the measures of stock market development are used in one singular regression which will give rise to bias in the regression results on account of multicollinearity between stock market development indicators and hence there is need for a regression model which will employ each measure of stock market development in turn in subsequent regressions of stock market development. This represents the second research gap that this study will bridge. Hence, in filling the two research gaps as earlier highlighted, this present study will make a significant contribution to knowledge in contributing to the literature on stock market development and foreign direct investment.

Methodology

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of this study is the capital market theory of foreign direct investment. The theory argues that FDI is attracted where the stock market is developed as reflected by an efficient market and fairly priced stocks. Intuitively, where stock prices are fair in the sense that they reflect the market fundamentals, it will attract foreigners to invest in Nigeria since the stock market which is a source of external finance can be accessed for borrowing of funds at low cost. Consequently foreign direct investment will be attracted to Nigeria.

Model Specification

This research study consisting of two objectives will be performed with the aid of two models. In achieving both objectives, three alternative stock market development indicators measuring the size and liquidity dimensions of the Nigeria stock market will be used to measure stock market development. The stock market development indicators are namely stock market capitalization ratio (measuring stock market size), turnover ratio and value of shares traded ratio (together

measuring stock market liquidity). The first objective of the study seeking to examine the direction of causality between stock market development and foreign direct investment in Nigeria will make use of a Granger causality model for the purpose. The Granger causality model as specified by Gujarati (2008) and adapted for use by this study is as in Equations (1) and (2) below:

$$FDI_t = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i STKMKTDEV_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i LOG FDI_{t-i} + \mu_{1t} \quad (1)$$

$$STKMKTDEV_t = \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i FDI_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^m \delta_i STKMKTDEV_{t-i} + \mu_{2t} \quad (2)$$

Where

FDI = Foreign direct investment; STKMKTDEV = Stock Market Development

The subscripts t refer to time periods and the disturbances μ_{1t} and μ_{2t} are assumed uncorrelated. Note that the above Granger causality equation is estimated in respect of each respective stock market development indicators namely, stock market capitalization ratio, turnover ratio and value of shares traded ratio. The above equation (1) states that present values of foreign direct investment are caused by stock market development (which will be measured by alternative indicators of market capitalization ratio, turnover ratio and Value of shares traded ratio) in addition to past values of foreign direct investment. On the other hand, Equation (2) states that present values of stock market development (which will be measured by alternative indicators of market capitalization ratio, turnover ratio and value of shares traded ratio) are caused by foreign direct investment in addition to past values of stock market development.

The model adopted by this study in respect of the second objective of this study which is to determine the impact of stock market development on foreign direct investment inflow to Nigeria is the modified model of Offiong and Atsu (2014). The model of Offiong and Atsu (2014) is specified below:

$$FDI = f(\text{GDP, Interest Rate, Wage rate, Trade Openness}) \quad (3)$$

The above model in Equation (3) is modified for this present study by replacing the independent variables, GDP, interest rate and Wage rate with respective stock market development indicators (namely, market capitalization ratio, turnover ratio and total value of shares traded ratio) introduced into the model one-at-a-time, as well as Real GDP per capita. The resultant model adopted for this study is as in Equation (4) below in its general form:

$$FDI = f(\text{STKMKTDEV, TOPEN, RGDPCC}) \quad (4)$$

$$FDI = f(\text{SMKTCAPR, TOVR, TVSTR}) \quad (5)$$

Where FDI = Foreign direct investment, STKMKTDEV = Stock market development (=f(SMKTCAPR, TOVR, TVSTR)), TOPEN = Trade openness, RGDPCC = Real GDP per capita.

Equation (4) above with Real GDP per capita transformed to logs and each stock market development indicator - market capitalization ratio, turnover ratio and Total value of shares traded ratio entering the model one-at-a-time, is transformed into an econometric model result as in Equations (6) – (8) below

$$FDI_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{SMKTCAPR}_t + \alpha_2 \text{TOPEN}_t + \alpha_3 \text{Log RGDPCC}_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (6)$$

Where,

FDI = Foreign direct investment; SMKTCAPR = Stock market capitalization ratio; TOPEN = Trade Openness; RGDPCC = Real GDP per capita

From the above equation (6), α_0 is the constant. $\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_3$ are the coefficients of the independent variables measuring the impact of a unit change in the independent variable on the dependent variable (foreign direct investment).

With respect to turnover ratio as the stock market development indicator, equation (7) is the econometric model to examine the impact of turnover ratio as a measure of stock market development (capturing stock market liquidity) on foreign direct investment.

$$FDI_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TOVR_t + \beta_2 TOPEN_t + \beta_3 \text{Log RGDP}PC_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (7)$$

Where, FDI = Foreign Direct Investment; TOVR = Turnover ratio; TOPEN = Trade Openness; RGDPCC = Real GDP per capita

From the above equation (7), β_0 is the constant. $\beta_1 \dots \beta_3$ are the coefficients of the independent variables measuring the impact of a unit change in the independent variable on the dependent variable (Foreign direct investment).

With respect to total value of shares traded ratio as the stock market development indicator (also measuring stock market liquidity), equation (8) is the econometric model to examine the impact of Total value of shares traded ratio as a measure of stock market development on foreign direct investment.

$$FDI_t = \varphi_0 + \varphi_1 TVSTR_t + \varphi_2 TOPEN_t + \varphi_3 \text{Log RGDP}PC_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (8)$$

Where, FDI = Foreign direct investment; TVSTR = Total value of stocks traded ratio; TOPEN = Trade Openness; RGDPCC = Real GDP per capita

From the above equation (7), φ_0 is the constant. $\varphi_1 \dots \varphi_3$ are the coefficients of the independent variables measuring the impact of a unit change in the independent variable on the dependent variable (Foreign Direct Investment).

In each of equations (6) to (8), the subscripts t denote the time period for this study and in the case of this study is 1981 – 2019. Further note that the introduction of the error term or stochastic variable into the model is to take into consideration other variables that can influence Foreign Direct Investment other than the ones stated in the model which are not captured by the model.

Note that Real GDP per capita enters the above model in log form in line with standard econometric practice so as to give rise to standardized coefficients or parameters for the model when it is estimated by regression. Further note that three stock market development indicators namely, stock market capitalization ratio, turnover ratio and total value of shares traded ratio, measuring different dimensions of the development of the Nigeria stock market will be employed in the above model as indicators of stock market development, with each indicator introduced into the model one-at-a-time on account of potential strong correlation between all the three indicators of stock market development.

Measurement of Variables

Stock Market Capitalization ratio (SMKTCAPR): This is a measure of stock market development measuring the size of the stock market. It is computed as: $\frac{\text{Stock market capitalization}}{GDP}$

Turnover Ratio (TOVR): This is a measure of stock market development measuring stock trading relative to the size of the stock market and is used as an index of comparison for market liquidity rating and level of transaction costs. The ratio is computed as: $\frac{\text{Total value of shares traded}}{\text{Stock market capitalization}}$

Total Value of Stocks Traded Ratio (TVSTR): This is a measure of stock market development measuring stock trading relative to the size of the economy as measured by GDP. It is also a measure of stock market liquidity and is computed as: $\frac{\text{Total value of share traded}}{\text{GDP}}$

Trade Openness (TOPEN): This is the degree to which Nigeria’s borders are open to the inflow and outflow of goods and services to and from Nigeria as the country engages in international trade. It is computed according to the international trade literature as: $\frac{\text{Value of Exports} + \text{Value of Imports}}{\text{GDP}}$.

Source of Data

Secondary data was employed by this study covering the period 1981 to 2019. Data on respective stock market development indicators (stock market capitalization ratio, turnover ratio and total value of shares traded ratio), interest rate and trade openness were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria Bulletin 2019, while data on FDI and Real GDP per capita were sourced from the World Bank World Development Indicators database.

Results and Discursion

Granger Causality Test Results For causality Between Stock Market Development Indicators and Foreign Direct Investment. Table 1.

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests(1981 2019).		Lags: 3	
Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
SMKTCAPR does not Granger Cause FDI	36	3.86483	0.0207
FDI does not Granger Cause SMKTCAPR	36	3.55625	0.0279
TOVR does not Granger Cause FDI	36	6.15893	0.0026
FDI does not Granger Cause TOVR	36	0.21570	0.8846
TVSTR does not Granger Cause FDI	36	13.0615	0.00002
FDI does not Granger Cause TVSTRGDP	36	3.47441	0.0303

Source: Author’s computation (2020)

From the above Table 1, the Granger causality test result indicates that there exists causality from Stock market capitalization ratio to Foreign direct investment inflow and vice versa. This is because the two test equations for the Granger causality test between Stock market capitalization ratio (SMKCAPR) and Foreign Direct Investment inflow (FDI) resulted in statistically significant F-statistics ($p < 0.05$). Thus there exists bi-directional causality between Stock market capitalization ratio (SMKCAPR) and Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Nigeria for the sample period of study. Also, the Granger causality test result indicates that there exists causality from turnover ratio to foreign direct investment inflow and no causality running from FDI to turn over ratio. This is because the test equation for causality from turnover ratio (TOVR) to Foreign direct investment inflow (FDI) resulted in a significant F-statistic of 6.15893 ($p < 0.05$), while the F-statistic for the test equation for causality from Foreign direct investment inflow (FDI) to turnover ratio (TOVR) is insignificant ($p > 0.05$). Thus there exists uni-directional causality between turnover ratio (TOVR) and Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) running from turnover ratio to FDI only for the sample period

of study in Nigeria. Finally, the Granger causality test result indicates that there exists causality from total value of stocks traded ratio to Foreign direct investment inflow and vice versa. This is because the two test equations for the Granger causality test between total value of stocks traded ratio (TVSTR) and Foreign Direct Investment inflow (FDI) resulted in statistically significant F-statistics ($p < 0.05$). Thus there exists bi-directional causality between total value of stocks traded ratio (TVSTR) and Foreign Direct Investment inflow (FDI) in Nigeria for the sample period of study.

Unit Root Test, Johansen Co-integration and Error Correction Model Results

This section presents the results and their discussion of the Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root test, Johansen co-integration test and Error correction model regressions results in achieving the second research objective of his study.

Unit Root Test

Unit root test is a test performed on time-series data prior to using the data in econometric analysis. The results of ADF unit root test performed on variables in this present study are presented in table 2.

Table 2. Summary of Augmented Dickey Fuller Unit Root Test Results

Variables	Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF)		Order of Integration
	Levels	First Difference	
FDI	-3.430653(0.0662)	-6.991665(0.0000)	I(1)
SMKTCAPR	-3.229759(0.0952)	-5.178954(0.0017)	I(1)
TOVR	-3.359797(0.0735)	-8.335848(0.0000)	I(1)
TVSTR	-3.148363(0.1114)	-4.461987(0.0076)	I(1)
TOPEN	-1.790032(0.6880)	-5.362977(0.0006)	I(1)
LOG RGDPPC	-2.307535(0.7629)	-4.648091(0.0005)	I(1)

Source: Author’s computation (2020)

From the above table 4, all the variables are non-stationary at levels and have to be differenced once to be stationary which gives the order of integration of the variables as I(1) as shown in the table. Note that the ADF test is performed at the 5% level of statistical significance.

Johansen Co-integration Test Result

Two or more variables are co-integrated if their linear combination forms a stationary relationship despite that individually the variables may not be stationary. The Johansen co-integration test is therefore valid in this present study on account that all variables employed in the respective models for the study are integrated of the same order 1. When variables are co-integrated it also implies that there exists a long run relationship between the variables being tested for co-integration. The below Tables 3 – 5 present results of the Johansen co-integration test for all the models specified for this study (that is; equations (5),(6) and (7)).

Table 3. Johansen Co-integration test result for Specified Model Equation (5)

Series: FDI SMKTCAPR TOPEN LOG RGDPPC							
Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 3							
Trace Test				Eigen Value Test			
H ₀	H ₁	Statistics	5% Critical Value	H ₀	H ₁	Statistics	5% Critical Value
r=0*	r≥1	87.29380	47.85613	r=0*	r≥1	43.33890	27.58434
r≤1*	r≥2	43.95490	29.79707	r≤1*	r≥2	30.51186	21.13162
r≤2	r≥3	13.44305	15.49471	r≤2	r≥3	9.337955	14.26460
r≤3*	r≥4	4.105091	3.841466	r≤3*	r≥4	4.105091	3.841466

Source: Author's computation (2020)* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

The above Table 3 indicates that there exist two co-integrating equations on the basis of both the trace test statistic and the Eigen value test statistic. Consequently, it is concluded that co-integration exists between Foreign direct investment (FDI), Sock market capitalization ratio (SMKTCAPR), Trade Openness (TOPEN), Log of Real GDP per capita (Log RGDPPC).

Table 4. Johansen Co-integration test result for Specified Model Equation (6)

Series: FDI TOVR TOPEN LOG RGDPPC							
Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 3							
Trace Test				Eigen Value Test			
H ₀	H ₁	Statistics	5% Critical Value	H ₀	H ₁	Statistics	5% Critical Value
r=0*	r≥1	60.22968	47.85613	r=0*	r≥1	28.13366	27.58434
r≤1	r≥2	28.12044	29.79707	r≤1	r≥2	19.59366	21.13162
r≤2	r≥3	12.78072	15.49471	r≤2	r≥3	9.739963	14.26460
r≤3*	r≥4	5.216162	3.841466	r≤3*	r≥4	4.060414	3.841466

Source: Author's computation (2020)* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

The above Table 4 indicates that there exists one co-integrating equation on the basis of both the trace test statistic and the Eigen value test statistic. Thus the null hypothesis of no co-integrating relationship is rejected and the alternative hypothesis of 1 co-integrating relationship (r≥1) is accepted. Consequently, it is concluded that co-integration exists between Foreign direct investment (FDI), Turnover Ratio (TOVR), Trade Openness (TOPEN), Log of Real GDP per capita (Log RGDPPC).

Table 5. Johansen Co-integration test result for Specified Model Equation (7)

Series: FDI TVSTR TOPEN LOG RGDPPC							
Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 3							
Trace Test				Eigen Value Test			
H ₀	H ₁	Statistics	5% Critical Value	H ₀	H ₁	Statistics	5% Critical Value
r=0*	r≥1	61.52769	47.85613	r=0*	r≥1	28.13366	27.58434
r≤1*	r≥2	33.39403	29.79707	r≤1	r≥2	19.59366	21.13162
r≤2	r≥3	13.80038	15.49471	r≤2	r≥3	9.739963	14.26460
r≤3*	r≥4	4.060414	3.841466	r≤3*	r≥4	4.060414	3.841466

Source: Author’s computation from (2020)* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level.

The above Table 5 indicates that there exist two co-integrating equations on the basis of the trace test statistic, while the Eigen value test statistic indicates the existence of one co-integrating equation. Consequently, it is concluded that co-integration exists between Foreign direct investment (FDI), Total value of stocks traded ratio (TVSTR), Trade Openness (TOPEN), Log of Real GDP per capita (Log RGDPPC).

Error Correction Model Regression Model Estimation Results

The summarized results of Error correction model regression of the respective models specified in Equations (5) – (7) are presented in Models (1) – (3) in the below tables 6 and 7.

Table 6. Over-parameterized Error Correction Model Regression Results

Model	(1)	(2)	(3)
Dependent Variable	FDI	FDI	FDI
Constant	0.051706(0.174054)	0.034783(0.176535)	0.002345(0.168861)
ECM (-1)	-0.899016***(0.4062)	-1.22787***(0.4626)	-1.3961***(0.4587)
D(SMKTCAPR)	-0.812081(3.864715)		
D(SMKTCAPR (-1))	1.713181(3.652639)		
D(SMKTCAPR (-2))	5.739886(4.897016)		

D(TOVR)		-0.000296(0.006161)	
D(TOVR(-1))		-0.003193(0.008995)	
D(TOVR(-2))		-0.014655(0.007637)	
D(TVSTR)			-0.003566(0.029040)
D(TVSTR(-1))			-0.009182(0.038212)
D(TVSTR(-2))			-0.062881(0.033128)
D(TOPEN)	14.56053**(6.199828)	8.968637(6.676198)	7.417828(7.554823)
D(TOPEN(-1))	9.754427(4.859972)	2.568606(6.237129)	4.755774(5.528993)
D(TOPEN(-2))	-7.563784(6.603751)	9.000962(6.079979)	-5.555942(6.585330)
D(Log RGDPPC)	- 5.627035**(2.660440)	-5.658426(2.952001)	-6.545237**(2.6105)
D(Log RGDPPC(-1))	3.251492(2.954913)	3.285031(3.016652)	4.123996(2.949100)
D(Log RGDPPC(-2))	-2.356194(2.584546)	-3.160846(2.808253)	-3.180001(2.609913)
D(FDI(-1))	0.457343(0.383616)	0.997943**(0.432871)	1.053173**(0.419877)
D(FDI(-2))	0.294942(0.201744)	0.431470(0.234797)	0.426506(0.222538)
D(FDI(-3))		0.245450(0.228737)	0.172670(0.251918)
R-Squared	0.698119	0.716490	0.756043
Durbin-Watson Stat	1.823435	1.991582	1.786066
F Statistic	3.854266***	3.499225***	4.291042***

** , *** , represent significance at 5% and 1% levels of significance.

Source: Author's computation (2020)

Table 7. Parsimonious Error Correction Model Regression Results

Model	(1)	(2)	(3)
Dependent Variable	FDI	FDI	FDI
Constant	-0.078667(0.15903)	-0.047445(0.155379)	-0.043357(0.140139)
ECM (-1)	-0.9245*** (0.2933)	-0.8837*** (0.3076)	-1.4017*** (0.3429)
D(SMKTCAPR)	-2.612270(2.922093)		
D(TOVR)		-0.001227(0.005407)	
D(TOVR(-1))		0.004876(0.006574)	
D(TOVR(-2))		-0.0160*** (0.0057)	

D(TVSTR)			-0.031247(0.020656)
D(TVSTR(-1))			0.014295(0.024827)
D(TVSTR(-2))			-0.0684**(0.0247)
D(TOPEN)	14.8495***(4.3234)	17.8468***(4.3313)	14.3961***(4.0472)
D(TOPEN(-1))	11.7139***(4.7434)		
D(Log RGDPPC)	-3.803165(2.432435)	-1.992937(2.425020)	-4.519150(2.194887)
D(FDI(-1))	0.328609(0.263637)	0.5669**(0.257436)	0.9836***(0.2913)
D(FDI(-2))			0.322663**(0.149952)
R-Squared	0.559956	0.622310	0.708527
Durbin Watson Statistic	1.780876	1.936209	1.880149
F Statistic	5.726240***	5.884554***	7.292556

**** , *** , represent significance at 5% and 1% levels of significance.**

Source: Author’s computation (2020)

From the above Table 7, interpreting the diagnostics of each of the models (1) – (3).The R-squared of Models (1), (2) and (3), 0.559956, 0.622310 and 0.708527 respectively. This means that while in model 1, 55.99% of changes in FDI are explained by changes in the respective independent variables, in Model 2, 62.23% of changes in FDI are explained by changes in the respective independent variables, and in Model 3, 70.85% of changes in FDI are explained by changes in the respective independent variables. The R-squared of all estimated models being high, indicates that all models fit the data substantially. With respect to the presence of autocorrelation in the estimated Error correction models, the Durbin-Watson statistics of 1.78, 1.94 and 1.88 of each of the models respectively indicate that there exists no autocorrelation in the estimated model since the Durbin-watson statistics are all approximately 2, and a Durbin-Watson statistic of two is the Rule of thumb for determining the presence of autocorrelation in econometric analysis. Finally, the F-statistic of the estimated models are an indication of an appropriately specified model where the F-statistic is significant at the 5% level. From the estimated models in table 7, the respective F-Statistics of each of the models are statistically significant at the 1% level. Therefore all models are correctly specified. Consequently as all diagnostics of the estimated models in table 7 above are acceptable, the results of estimation are interpreted and discussed.

ECM(-1) in table 7 above is the Error correction term of the respective estimated models. Each model has a unique Error correction term, and all are negatively signed and statistically significant at the 1% level which validates the error correction model. The error correction model regression was estimated on the evidence of the co-integration between variables in respective models as observed from the co-integration table 3-5. The error correction term provides the speed of adjustment from short run disequilibrium. That is the percentage of the error in the previous period that will be corrected in the current period. The above table 10 indicates that in respect of model 1, 92.45% of errors in the previous period will be corrected in the current period as the coefficient of the error correction term is -0.924457. From Model (2), the coefficient of the error correction term of -0.883732 indicates that 88.37% of errors in the previous period will be corrected in the current period, while in model (3) the coefficient of the error correction term of

-1.401705 indicates that 140.17% of errors in the previous period will be corrected in the current period. The respective speeds of adjustment from short run disequilibrium of all the models (1) – (3) are all quite high and indicate that the respective error correction model estimations are performing models over the long run.

The stock market development indicators from each of the estimated models as observed from table 9 are all insignificant with respect to the current values of the indicators. The coefficient of change in current stock market capitalization ratio (SMKTCAPR) is -2.612270, the coefficient of change in current Turnover ratio (TOVR) is -0.001227, and the coefficient of change in current total value of stocks traded ratio (TVSTR) is -0.031247. The one period lagged value of turnover ratio and total value of stocks traded ratio are however positive but insignificant for FDI inflow in Nigeria as the coefficient of change in the one-period lagged value of turnover ratio (D(TOVR(-1))) is 0.004876, and the coefficient of change in the one-period lagged value of total value of stocks traded ratio is 0.014295. Stock market development indicators of turnover ratio and total value of stocks traded ratio begin to have a significant influence on FDI inflow two periods after the current period. The two-period lagged values of turnover ratio and total value of stocks traded ratio are both negative and significant for FDI inflow in Nigeria. The coefficient of change in the two-period lagged value of turnover ratio (D(TOVR(-2))) is -0.016022 and the coefficient of change in the two-period lagged value of total value of stocks traded ratio is -0.068350 and both coefficients are statistically significant at the 1% level of significance. In general, therefore, a negative impact is found of all stock market development indicators on FDI inflow to Nigeria and this goes against the a priori expectations of this study. The finding of this study as regards stock market capitalization ratio having a negative impact on FDI inflow to Nigeria goes against the findings of Bala-Umar et al (2015). However the finding may be explained in that a larger stock market may result in the presence of inefficient firms in the stock market and hence the presence of low quality stocks which may discourage foreign investors seeking to bring FDI to Nigeria.

The finding of negative impact of turnover ratio on foreign direct investment inflow to Nigeria is consistent with findings by Bala-Umar et al (2015), and Ezeoha, Ebele, Ndi, and Okereke (2009) who make similar findings. The finding may be explained by poor management of liquidity of the Nigeria stock exchange, and may result where all market entrants participating on the stock exchange are not having equitable access to the benefits of trading on the stock exchange. Further poor liquidity management plays a role in respect of total value of stocks traded ratio which is found to have a negative impact on FDI inflow to Nigeria. This finding goes against the finding of Bala-Umar et al (2015), who find that total value of stocks traded ratio boosts FDI inflow to Nigeria.

The negative impact of stock market development as measured by alternative indicators of stock market development in this study highlight a concern for Nigeria's prospects of achieving a boost in Foreign Direct Investment inflow using the Nigeria stock exchange as a veritable tool in doing so. The intent of the stock market to serve as a veritable tool for accessing needed funds by multinational enterprises seeking to establish in Nigeria through FDI. However the findings of this study demonstrate the low level of development of the Nigeria stock exchange and while this low level of development is not peculiar to Nigeria, there exists the need for urgent steps to be taken by the Nigeria government to ensure that the Nigeria stock exchange acts as one of the channels through which increased FDI can be attracted to Nigeria in the future.

With respect to the control variables in all estimated models presented in table 7 above, changes in current trade openness is positive and significant for FDI inflow in all models, but in model (1) only, the coefficient of one period lag of trade openness is also positive and statistically significant

in addition to coefficient of current trade openness. Real GDP per capita is negative but insignificant across all the models for FDI inflow to Nigeria. Finally, one period lag of FDI while positive but insignificant for FDI inflow in Model (1), it is positive and statistically significant for FDI inflow in models (2) and (3). In addition in model (3) two periods lagged FDI inflow is positive and significant for current FDI inflow as the coefficient of two periods lagged change in FDI is 0.322663 and is statistically significant.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study investigated stock market development and foreign direct investment in Nigeria over the period of 1981 to 2019. Granger causality and ADF unit root test, Johansen co-integration and Error correction model regression were used to analyze data. The findings of this study as regards Granger causality highlights the need for the consideration of causality between various stock market development indicators and FDI by the Nigeria government in undertaking stock market reforms to drive FDI inflow to Nigeria. The error correction model regression results on the other hand, highlight the need for urgent stock market reforms towards positioning the Nigeria stock market as a veritable tool for attracting invaluable foreign direct investment inflow for the benefit of the Nigeria economy. The findings of this study are expected to drive future policy of stock market development and FDI inflow to Nigeria.

Policy Recommendations

This study recommends based on its findings that urgent and appropriately sequenced stock market reforms be undertaken so as to reverse the adverse effects of stock market development indicators on FDI inflow. Further increased financial openness of the Nigeria economy should be promoted as part of financial liberalization reforms so as to attract efficient firms that will use borrowed funds efficiently to the Nigeria stock exchange. In addition, tight and continuous monitoring of the quality of listed firms on the Nigeria stock exchange should be maintained by the securities and exchange commission of Nigeria stock exchange to promote the credibility of the stock exchange to multinational enterprises seeking to establish in Nigeria through FDI and will be able to access funds from suppliers of credit on the stock exchange. Finally a level playing field should be set for all firms listed on the stock exchange to promote equitable access to the benefits of the stock exchange and which will consequently ensure the participation of both domestic and foreign stock market participants on the exchange and will boost liquidity of the market and ensure a vital contribution to be made by the Nigeria stock exchange to the benefit of the Nigeria economy.

References

- Adam, A. M., & G. Tweneboah(2008) "Foreign direct investment (FDI) and stock market development: Ghana evidence" *Munich Personal Repec Archive* (MPRA) Paper No. 11261.
- Afeez, A.S & B.A. Kazeem (2010). 'The Stock Market and Economic Growth in Nigeria'. *An Empirical Investigation, Journal of Economic Theory, 4, 65-70*.
- Aigbovo, O & A.O. Izekor (2015). Stock market development and Economic growth in Nigeria, *Journal of social management, 1(8), 6-18*.
- Amagwu, C.A (2016). Impact of financial liberalization on the development of the nigeria capital market (1984-2014) Unpublished B.Sc. (Economics) Dissertation. Department of Economics, Accounting and Finance, Bells University of Technology, Ota, Ogun State, Nigeria.
- Bala-Umar, M., S. Ismail & Z. Sulong (2015). The Impact of Stock Market Development on Foreign Direct Investment in Nigeria: An Application of Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model. *Scholars Journal of Economics, Business and Management, 2(4):400-411*.
- Boermans, M., H.J. Roelfsema, & Z. Yi, (2009). Regional determinants of FDI in China: A new approach with recent data. *Discussion Paper Series/Tjalling C. Koopmans Research Institute, 9(23)*
- Ezeoha A, O. Ebele, O. NdiOkereke (2009). Stock market development and private investment growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa,; 11(2):20-35*.
- Idenyi, O. S., A. C. Ifeyinwa, N. J. Obinna, & E. A. Promise (2016). Impact of Foreign Direct Investment on Stock Market Growth in Nigeria. *Asian Research Journal of Arts & Social Sciences, 1(2): 1-14, 2016*
- KMMCB, K. (2015). Macroeconomic factors and stock market development: With special reference to Colombo Stock Exchange. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, 1-7*.
- Levine, R. (2003). More on Finance and Growth: More Finance, More Growth?. *Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis Review, Vol. 85 (4): pp 31 – 45*.
- Olugbenga, A. A., & O. O. Grace (2015). Impact of Foreign Direct Investment on Nigerian Capital Market Development. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences, 5(1), 103-108*.
- Omodero, C. O., & M. C. Ekwe (2017). Impact of Foreign Direct Investment (Fdi) On the Stock Market Performances in Nigeria (1985-2014). *Applied Finance and Accounting, 3(1), 36-48*.
- Omoruyi, A., & U. Ahmed (2014). Financial System Development and Economic Growth the Nigerian Stock Market and Bank Perspective. *Asian Journal of Business Management, 6(4), 155-172*.
- Oseni, I. O., & O. S. Enilolobo (2011). Effect of foreign direct investment and stock market development on economic growth in Nigeria (1980-2009). *European Journal of Business and Management, 3(12), 34-42*.
- UNCTAD, Global Value Chains (2013). Investment and Trade for Development. *World Investment Report*.
- UNCTAD (2014). Foreign direct investment to Africa maintains momentum sustained by intra-African flows, UNCTAD Report reveals. Accessed 2 January 2018. [online] <<http://unctad.org/en/pages/PressRelease.aspx?OriginalVersionID=189>>